

KLIPPEL-TRENAUNAY-WEBER SYNDROME IN PALESTINIAN NEONATE: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT Background: Palestinian neonate was diagnosed from the first day of life as a case of Klippel-Trenaunay-Weber syndrome (KTWS). **Case summary:** She was full term and female newborn. After birth, on physical examination, she had hypertrophied right lower leg with port-wine stained. X-ray of lower limbs showed; right-sided hypertrophied soft tissue. Duplex ultrasonography of both lower limbs showed: right-sided limb muscles are hypertrophied when compared to the left-sided limb. The right-sided limb had prominent intramuscular vasculature mainly involving vastus medialis muscle. After two days of admission as a case of Klippel-Trenaunay-Weber syndrome, the baby was discharged home in good general condition. **Conclusion:** Early diagnosis of Klippel-Trenaunay-Weber syndrome in neonatal period results in better prognosis and less complication.

KEYWORDS Klippel-Trenaunay-Weber syndrome, port-wine stain, neonate

Introduction

Klippel-Trenaunay-Weber syndrome is a rare congenital condition has clinical triad [1-2-3]:

- Cutaneous capillary haemangioma is mostly port-wine stain which is available since birth in the majority of cases.
- Soft tissue and bone hypertrophy of one limb, the lower limb is affected more than upper limb.
- Varicose veins.

The condition has a variable presentation. Not all clinical triad is available at birth, the hypertrophy of the limb and varicose maybe will take few years for one or two of them to be apparent. Internal organs and more than one limb may be affected. Klippel-Trenaunay-Weber syndrome could associate with arterial malformation and lymphatic drainage. Klippel-Trenaunay-Weber syndrome has low blood velocity flow in mal-

formed vessels whereas Parkes Weber's syndrome has high blood velocity flow in arteriovenous malformations. Male and female are equally affected. Klippel-Trenaunay-Weber syndrome is sporadic disorder although limited cases were known to be familiar. The aetiology of the disorder is still unknown. Klippel-Trenaunay-Weber syndrome is a clinical diagnosis which is confirmed by the imaging; MRI, Doppler ultrasound, and angiography.

Case report:

The parents were nonconsanguineous, they had no family history of congenital diseases, the mother was G8P7, the baby was full term female, and the delivery was by normal vaginal delivery. Birth weight was 3700 grams, and Apgar score was 8, nine at 1, 5 minutes respectively. After birth on routine physical examination, the baby was found to have: the right lower limb is hypertrophied, and it is covered by port wine stain [Figure 1]. The other parts of physical examination were normal. Brain, abdominal ultrasound, and echocardiography studies were normal. Blood culture result was no growth. X-ray of lower limbs showed; right-sided hypertrophied soft tissue [Figure 2]. Duplex ultrasonography of both lower limbs showed: right-sided limb muscles are hypertrophied when compared to the left-sided limb. The right-sided limb had prominent intramuscular vasculature mainly involving vastus medialis muscle. The multidisciplinary team consists of orthopaedic, vascular surgeon, plastic surgeon,

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Figure 1: The right lower limb is hypertrophied, and port wine stain covers it

social worker and neonatologist was involved in the management of the patient as Klippel-Trenaunay-Weber syndrome case which needs close monitoring and follows up to prevent fatal complication and delay intervention.

DISCUSSION

KTWS is a rare congenital disorder. Clinical triad characterises the affected limb; cutaneous hemangioma, varicose veins and hypertrophied soft tissue and bone. The disorder has variable presentations. The condition was rarely diagnosed at the neonatal age [4] as the clinical picture still incomplete. The baby was full term female, on routine examination after birth, she found to have the right lower limb covered entirely port wine stain and hypertrophied compared to the left lower limb. The other parts of physical examination were normal. The X-ray showed the right lower limb was hypertrophied, the duplex ultrasonography of both lower limbs showed; the right lower limb is hypertrophied and had prominent intramuscular vasculature compared to the left lower limb. By Duplex ultrasonography as arteriovenous malformations (AVMs) were not available, Parkes Weber's syndrome was excluded. As the baby had not spinal or paraspinous (AVMs), seizure or scoliosis, CLOVE syndrome (Congenital lipomatous overgrowth, vascular malformations, and epidermal nevi)[5] and Cobb syndrome[6] were ruled out. The clinical picture of the baby did not match the diagnosis of Sturge Weber syndrome[7] as there was no facial port wine stain and brain ultrasound was normal. The clinical picture of the baby is consistent with the KTWS diagnosis. There was two feature of the clinical triad; hypertrophied soft tissue and port wine stain of the right lower limb. From start social worker, plastic surgeon, pediatric orthopaedic, vascular surgeon, and neonatologist were involved. Team plan recommended close monitoring and follow up to prevent morbid course like, cellulitis, limb length discrepancy, limb hypertrophy or atrophy and deep venous thrombosis.

Conclusion

A rare case of KTWS was diagnosed after birth, and the case was managed by the multidisciplinary team which will make

Figure 2: X-ray of lower limbs showed; right-sided hypertrophied soft tissue

the prognosis is better with less complication.

Authors' Statements

Competing Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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